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Comparati

Connecting and visualizing data: a Knowledge Base of Germanic Cultural Heritage items in Venice

UNIONE EUROPEA
Fondo Sociale Europeo

Ministero dell'Università
e della Ricerca

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RICERCA
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2014 - 2020

REACT EU

The project

- The OntoVE project has as its goal the creation of a knowledge graph of Germanic Cultural Heritage (CH) items linked to Venice and the Veneto region.
- The goal is to provide uniform metadata descriptions of heterogeneous objects, often catalogued through heterogeneous metadata in order to make them retrievable through the same platform.
- The second goal consists in providing different visualization outputs that cater to a different audience.
- The project is funded by the Italian National Operational Plan (PON) on Research and Innovation 2014-2020 and the European Social Fund (ESF) within the Recovery assistance for cohesion and the territories of Europe (REACT-EU)
- It is moreover carried out in close collaboration with the partner IT company Net7.

Heterogeneous dataset

- The dataset included consists of a specific portion of real world-knowledge: Germanic CH artefacts linked to the Veneto region.
- This dataset ranges from archaeological findings dating back to the first populations that transited in the region (Goths and Lombards, from the 5th century onwards) to written documents, such as imperial charters.
- The individuals included in the dataset are already digitised in different online repositories.
- This leads to different metadata descriptions about them.

Heterogeneous dataset

- Location of the relevant individuals through the querying of online catalogues and the scrutiny of scientific papers.
- Prominent resource for archaeological findings is constituted by the General Catalogue of Italian Cultural Heritage (<https://catalogo.beniculturali.it/>), a Open Data initiative of the Ministry for Culture.
- Other relevant archaeological findings are hosted by institutions outside of Italy and available through different repositories, such as the online database of the British Museum.
- This results in heterogeneous metadata formats in need of a uniform description.
- Similar conclusions can be drawn for documentary findings.

Semantic alignment operations

The Ontove_Archeo and Ontove_WrittenRecords modules

- One of the first outputs of the project consisted in the creation of two ontological modules aimed at describing archaeological and documentary CH items.
- Semantic alignment operations between abstract domain ontologies such as CIDOC-CRM, v. 7.1.2 (Bekiari et al. 2022) and LRMoo, v. 0.9.6 (Bekiari et al. 2023) with fine-grained ontologies such as ArCo (Carriero et al. 2019) and Bibframe (<https://www.loc.gov/bibframe/implementation/index.html>).
- CIDOC-CRM and LRMoo provide abstract classes and properties that allow for an adequate description of CH items, but are in need of finer-grained classes to better capture the features of said items, since they are resistant to concrete implementation (Barzaghi, Palmirani and Peroni 2022).
- The relevant individuals are then described according to the Ontove_Archeo and Ontove_WrittenRecords modules through Protégé Desktop, version 5.5.0 (<http://protege.stanford.edu>, Musen 2015).

Some examples

CIDOC-CRM E36_Visual_Item >
E37_Mark > E34_Inscription

ArCo: **AffixedElement**

- Brand
- CoatOfArms
- CoinDesign
- CounterStamp
- Emblem
- HistoricalPlaque
- Inscription

Some examples

LRMoo **F5_Instance** = Bibframe **Instance**

Subclasses of Bibframe Instance:

Print

Archival

Tactile

Electronic

Microform

Finer grained classes assigned as subclasses of the more general and abstract ones: more adequate description of CH items

Visualization

The description of the relevant individuals through two ontological modules has at its base the following competency questions:

- Which written sources can we find for the period A-B?
- In which period or in which area is written production to be found?
- Which archaeological artefacts present inscriptions?
- In which area are CH items belongin to the Cultural Scope X to be found?

In order to answer them, a SPARQL Endpoint based on Apache-Jena-Fuseki-4.7.0 (<https://jena.apache.org/index.html>) has been set up (now on a local VM)

Although SPARQL is the most powerful and effective way to navigate a knowledge graph, it is a possibility reserved to users with the relevant expertise.

Visualization

In light of the Faro Convention (<https://www.coe.int/en/web/culture-and-heritage/faro-convention>), we would like to open our dataset to non-expert users.

These include:

- academic users who do not necessarily have knowledge of SPARQL but want to explore the dataset;
- non-academic users who want to discover the history of the Veneto region.

The Sampo-UI portal

Reuse of the Sampo-UI model: the Semantic Computing Research Group (SeCo) has been releasing a series of semantic portals that provide different perspectives of the same data and enhance their discovery. The Sampo-UI model is open source and allows to customise different search perspectives.

The search perspectives show the results of SPARQL queries that work at the backend level, and allow the users to filter data: more intuitive exploration of the data.

The Sampo- UI portal

The OntoVE Sampo-Ui portal is therefore connected to the Fuseki SPARQL Endpoint.

It allows to explore data through the following search perspectives:

Entities: Archeological artefacts and their related chronology, cultural scope and bibliography.

Locations: Archaeological artefacts and their current location.

Works: Written documents and their related chronology, context and place of redaction.

Places: places mentioned in written documents.

Related Resources: works cited in the written documents included in the Knowledge Graph.

Events: events mentioned in the written documents, participants involved and work in which they are cited.

The Sampo-UI portal

OntoVE

Ontologie per la descrizione del patrimonio culturale germanico in Veneto

Select a perspective to search and browse the knowledge graph:

Works
Diplomi degli imperatori germanici riguardanti i territori veneti

Events
Informazioni sugli eventi legati ai documenti

Places

Locations

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The OntoVE portal starting page

The Sampo-UI portal

OntoVE Search all content

WORKS EVENTS PLACES **LOCATIONS** ENTITIES RELATEDRESOURCES INFO INSTRUCTIONS EN

Locations

Results: 48 Locations

Narrow down by:

Current Location

link

TABLE

EXPORT

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Archaeological Property	Current Location	link
Bead12 ...	Palazzo Folco (SOPRINTENDENZA ARCHEOLOGIA, BELLE ARTI E PAESAGGIO PER L'AREA METROPOLITANA DI VENEZIA E LE PROVINCE DI BELLUNO, PADOVA E TREVISO) ...	https://www.soprintendenzapdve.beniculturali.it/soprintendenza/le-sedi/palazzo-folco-la-ca-del-figo/
Corredo funerario longobardo, Tomba 32 ...	Depositi Soprintendenza Archeologia del Veneto, nucleo operativo di Verona ...	http://www.sbap-vr.beniculturali.it/
Bead4 ...	Palazzo Folco (SOPRINTENDENZA ARCHEOLOGIA, BELLE ARTI E PAESAGGIO PER L'AREA METROPOLITANA DI VENEZIA E LE PROVINCE DI BELLUNO, PADOVA E TREVISO) ...	https://www.soprintendenzapdve.beniculturali.it/soprintendenza/le-sedi/palazzo-folco-la-ca-del-figo/
Alemannic brooch 2 ...	Civico Museo Archeologico Milano ...	https://www.geonames.org/8133600/museo-archeologico.html
Lantfridus' Tombstone ...	Museo Archeologico Nazionale di Venezia ...	https://www.geonames.org/11994992/museo-archeologico-nazionale.html
Remains of noble Lombard chieftain ...	Tomb of Castelvint fort	-
Corredo funerario longobardo 1, Tomba 81 ...	Depositi Soprintendenza Archeologia del Veneto, nucleo operativo di Verona ...	http://www.sbap-vr.beniculturali.it/
Buckle ...	Palazzo Folco (SOPRINTENDENZA ARCHEOLOGIA, BELLE ARTI E PAESAGGIO PER L'AREA METROPOLITANA DI VENEZIA E LE PROVINCE DI BELLUNO, PADOVA E TREVISO) ...	https://www.soprintendenzapdve.beniculturali.it/soprintendenza/le-sedi/palazzo-folco-la-ca-del-figo/
Alemannic Brooch 1 ...	Civico Museo Archeologico Milano ...	https://www.geonames.org/8133600/museo-archeologico.html

The “Locations” perspective

The Sampo-UI portal

The screenshot shows the 'Locations' section of the OntoVE portal. The top navigation bar includes 'WORKS', 'EVENTS', 'PLACES', 'LOCATIONS' (highlighted), 'ENTITIES', 'RELATEDRESOURCES', 'INFO', 'INSTRUCTIONS', and 'EN'. A search bar is present with the text 'Search all content'. Below the navigation, the 'Locations' section is titled 'Locations' with an information icon. It shows 'Results: 48 Locations' and a 'Narrow down by:' section. The 'Current Location' filter is active, showing a list of checkboxes for various locations, including 'Palazzo Folco (SOPRINTENDENZA ARCHEC...', 'Corredo funerario longobardo 1, Tomba 81', 'Lombard Grave Goods 1, Tomb 81 [8]', 'Corredo funerario longobardo, Tomba 32 [8]', 'Lombard Grave Goods 2, Tomb 32 [8]', 'Sepolture di tre donne alemanne con abiti tr...', 'Tombs of three Alemannic women with trac...', 'Civico Museo Archeologico Milano [2]', 'Depositi Soprintendenza Archeologia del Ve...', and 'Mel [2]'. Below the filter, there is a 'link' dropdown menu. The main content area displays a table of results with columns for 'Archaeological Property', 'Current Location', and 'link'. The table includes rows for 'Bead12 ...', 'Corredo funerario longobardo, Tomba 32 ...', 'Bead4 ...', 'Alemannic brooch 2 ...', 'Lantfridus' Tombstone ...', 'Remains of noble Lombard chieftain ...', 'Corredo funerario longobardo 1, Tomba 81 ...', 'Buckle ...', and 'Alemannic Brooch 1 ...'. Each row provides a brief description of the location and a corresponding URL.

Locations *i*

Results: 48 Locations

Narrow down by:

Current Location *i*

Search...

- Palazzo Folco (SOPRINTENDENZA ARCHEC
- Corredo funerario longobardo 1, Tomba 81
- Lombard Grave Goods 1, Tomb 81 [8]
- Corredo funerario longobardo, Tomba 32 [8]
- Lombard Grave Goods 2, Tomb 32 [8]
- Sepolture di tre donne alemanne con abiti tr
- Tombs of three Alemannic women with trac
- Civico Museo Archeologico Milano [2]
- Depositi Soprintendenza Archeologia del Ve
- Mel [2]

link *i*

EXPORT

TABLE

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Archaeological Property <i>i</i>	Current Location <i>i</i>	link <i>i</i>
<i>▼</i> Bead12 ...	Palazzo Folco (SOPRINTENDENZA ARCHEOLOGIA, BELLE ARTI E PAESAGGIO PER L'AREA METROPOLITANA DI VENEZIA E LE PROVINCE DI BELLUNO, PADOVA E TREVISO) ...	https://www.soprintendenzapdve.beniculturali.it/soprintendenza/le-sedi/palazzo-folco-la-ca-del-figo/
<i>▼</i> Corredo funerario longobardo, Tomba 32 ...	Depositi Soprintendenza Archeologia del Veneto, nucleo operativo di Verona ...	http://www.sbp-vr.beniculturali.it/
<i>▼</i> Bead4 ...	Palazzo Folco (SOPRINTENDENZA ARCHEOLOGIA, BELLE ARTI E PAESAGGIO PER L'AREA METROPOLITANA DI VENEZIA E LE PROVINCE DI BELLUNO, PADOVA E TREVISO) ...	https://www.soprintendenzapdve.beniculturali.it/soprintendenza/le-sedi/palazzo-folco-la-ca-del-figo/
<i>▼</i> Alemannic brooch 2 ...	Civico Museo Archeologico Milano ...	https://www.geonames.org/8133600/museo-archeologico.html
<i>▼</i> Lantfridus' Tombstone ...	Museo Archeologico Nazionale di Venezia ...	https://www.geonames.org/11994992/museo-archeologico-nazionale.html
<i>▼</i> Remains of noble Lombard chieftain ...	Tomb of Castelvint fort	-
<i>▼</i> Corredo funerario longobardo 1, Tomba 81 ...	Depositi Soprintendenza Archeologia del Veneto, nucleo operativo di Verona ...	http://www.sbp-vr.beniculturali.it/
<i>▼</i> Buckle ...	Palazzo Folco (SOPRINTENDENZA ARCHEOLOGIA, BELLE ARTI E PAESAGGIO PER L'AREA METROPOLITANA DI VENEZIA E LE PROVINCE DI BELLUNO, PADOVA E TREVISO) ...	https://www.soprintendenzapdve.beniculturali.it/soprintendenza/le-sedi/palazzo-folco-la-ca-del-figo/
<i>▼</i> Alemannic Brooch 1 ...	Civico Museo Archeologico Milano ...	https://www.geonames.org/8133600/museo-archeologico.html

The “Locations” filtering options

The Sampo-UI portal

OntoVE Search all content WORKS EVENTS PLACES LOCATIONS ENTITIES RELATEDRESOURCES INFO INSTRUCTIONS EN

Works

Results: 8 Works

Narrow down by:

- publicationExpression
- originPlace
- issuer
- subject

Search...

- Verona [6]
- Carlo Magno [6]
- Vicenza [5]
- Cividale del Friuli [3]
- Aio, il Longobardo [2]
- Unknown [1]
- Oderzo [1]
- Abate Ferox [1]
- Liutprando garantisce possedimenti al M
- Restituzione dei possedimenti a Aio da t

TABLE EXPORT

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Label	publicationExpression	originPlace	issuer
Italia Sacra, Ferdinando Ughelli	-	-	-
Secondo Diploma di Carlo Magno del 04-08-792	Edizione del diploma 174 nei dMGH	Ratisbona	Carlo Magno
Diploma di Carlo Magno di Gennaio/Giugno 797	Edizione del Diploma 183 nei dMGH	Aquisgrana	Carlo Magno
Diploma di Carlo Magno del 04-08-792	Edizione del Diploma 175 nei dMGH	Ratisbona	Carlo Magno
Diploma di Carlo Magno del 02-02-799	Edizione del Diploma 187 nei dMGH	Aquisgrana	Carlo Magno
Diploma di Carlo Magno del 31-03-794	Edizione del Diploma 177 nei dMGH	Francoforte	Carlo Magno
Diploma di Carlo Magno del 07-07-809	Edizione del Diploma 209 nei dMGH	Aquisgrana	Carlo Magno
Diploma di Pipino il Breve, probabilmente falso	-	-	-

The “Works” perspective filtering options

CHIt-OntoVE Collaboration

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- Third visualization output thanks to the joint efforts between OntoVE and another PON project conducted at Ca' Foscari, CHIt (implemented by Giulia Fabbris with Net7).
 - The CHIt aggregator, powered by Muruca, collects data stored in different repositories and makes them available through the same platform, providing uniform metadata for them.
 - Possibility to annotate the data through the open source tool Pundit
 - Model can be applied to other Knowledge Graphs by the CHIt aggregator, thereby resulting in a protocol for the retrieval of data stored in SPARQL Endpoints.

CHIt-OntoVE Collaboration

The screenshot displays a web interface for searching records. On the left, there is a sidebar with a search box labeled 'Search in titles' and a 'Subjects' section containing a list of terms: 'map', 'manuscript', 'ww1', 'art', and 'archaeology'. The main content area shows '4 Tales' results. The first result is 'Casteldardo struttura di fortificazione', with provenance 'Trichiana' and subject 'Germanic Philology'. The second is 'Lastra sepolcrale di Lantfrido', with provenance 'Museo Archeologico Nazionale di Venezia' and subject 'Germanic Philology'. The third is 'Fibula a disco', with provenance 'British Museum' and subject 'Germanic Philology'. The fourth is 'Rocca di Castelvint', with provenance 'Mel' and subject 'Germanic Philology'. At the bottom of the results, there are navigation buttons (back, forward, first, last) and a 'Show n results: 12' dropdown menu.

Resources retrieved from the SPARQL query and visualized in the CHIt frontend

CHIt-OntoVE Collaboration

Metadata	Query	Archprop	
		Archprop	http://www.semanticweb.org/utente/ontologies/2023//OntoVE_Archeo#Castelvint_fort
		Label	Rocca di Castelvint
		LabelLoc	Mel
		ExternalLink	https://www.geonames.org/3173644/mel.html
		Bibliographies	http://www.semanticweb.org/utente/ontologies/2023//OntoVE_Archeo#Castelvint_fort_Catalogue_of_Cultural_Heritage_pdf_entry , http://www.semanticweb.org/utente/ontologies/2023//OntoVE_Archeo#Necropoli_d_i_Età_longobarda_nel_Veneto , http://www.semanticweb.org/utente/ontologies/2023//OntoVE_Archeo#Necropoli_l_ongobarde_in_Italia:_indirizzi_della_ricerca_e_nuovi_dati:_atti_del_Convegno_internazionale_26-28_settembre_2011,_Castello_del_Buonconsiglio,_Trento , http://www.semanticweb.org/utente/ontologies/2023//OntoVE_Archeo#Luoghi_e_segni_della_morte_in_età_in_età_longobarda:_tradizione_e_transizione_nelle_pratiche_dell'aristocrazia
		References	https://catalogo.beniculturali.it/detail/ArchaeologicalProperty/0500591271 , Elisa Possenti. 2001. «Necropoli di Età longobarda nel Veneto» Quaderni Friulani di Archeologia XI (XI): 133-52., NECROPOLI LONGOBARDE IN ITALIA Indirizzi della ricerca e nuovi dati (PRIMA PARTE) Atti del Convegno Internazionale 26 - 28 settembre 2011 Castello del Buonconsiglio, Trento a cura di Elisa Possenti PROVINCIA AUTONOMA DI TRENTO CASTELLO DEL BUONCONSIGLIO MONUMENTI E COLLEZIONI PROVINCIALI 2014, Caterina Giostra Luoghi e segni della morte in età in età longobarda: tradizione e transizione nelle pratiche dell'aristocrazia [A stampa in Archeologia e Società tra Tardo Antico e Alto Medioevo, a cura di G. P. Brogiolo, A. Chavarria, Mantova 2007, pp. 311-344 © dell'autrice - Distribuito in formato digitale da "Reti Medievali", www.retimedievali.it].
		Id	http://www.semanticweb.org/utente/ontologies/2023//OntoVE_Archeo#0500591271
		RepoLink	https://catalogo.beniculturali.it/detail/ArchaeologicalProperty/0500591271

An example of CHIt metadata description of an OntoVE item

Outlook

Adherence to the FAIR principles thanks to the reuse of established models.

Documentation available at:

<https://github.com/ChiDeBa/ontove>

(under implementation)

Sampo-UI portal and Apache-Jena-Fuseki SPARQL Endpoint will be available through a dedicated unive domain.

Further testing of the solidity of the model and the usability of the platform needed.

Thank you for your attention!

Let's keep in touch: chiara.debastiani@unive.it

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